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Effects of Audit Quality Report Disclosure on the Financial Performance of Deposit-taking SACCO's in Nairobi County

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Abstract

The financial sector in Kenya, particularly the Savings and Credit Cooperative Organizations (SACCOs), plays a crucial role in providing financial services to a significant portion of the population. SACCOs are vital for promoting financial inclusion, economic development, and social welfare, making regulation of the sector highly critical. Despite enhanced regulatory efforts by SASRA that places more attention on financial reporting, transparency and accountability through mandatory disclosures, there is limited empirical evidence on the impact of these regulation disclosures on the financial performance of SACCOs in Nairobi County. Therefore, the study sought to fill the gap in literature by examining the effect of regulation disclosures and financial performance of deposit taking Sacco's in Nairobi County. The study is guided by four key theories, namely; Agency theory, Signaling theory, Legitimacy theory, and Information Asymmetry Theory. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The target population of the study comprised of all the 601 employees drawn from accounting department and management levels from all the 49 DT-Sacco's with operations in Nairobi County. Stratified random sampling technique was used to select the study sample from all the 49 Saccos. Simple random sampling technique was utilized to administer questionnaires to the sample frame that comprise of accountants and managers from these firms. The study utilized Krejcie and Morgan formula to arrive at a study sample size of 264 respondents, which increased by 30% to cater for the random error and non-response. The study was based on quantitative data where both descriptive and inferential analysis techniques were used to establish the effect regulation disclosures on the financial performance of SACCOs in Nairobi County. Linear regression was used to determine the extent the predictor variable influence financial performance of Deposit taking Saccos' in Nairobi County. Validity and reliability tests were conducted to ensure that instruments used are reliable and measure the contracts targeted by the study. The study revealed high adherence to disclosure practices across all four variables: audit quality (M = 4.08, SD = 0.36), capital adequacy (M = 4.03, SD = 0.78), liquidity (M = 4.08, SD = 0.42), and governance (M = 4.12, SD = 0.41), indicating strong compliance and risk management frameworks among SACCOs. However, the explanatory power of these disclosures on financial performance was low, with audit quality (7.4%), capital adequacy (5.3%), liquidity (3.3%), and governance (3.4%) showing weak or negative correlations with ROE. This suggests that while these practices enhance stability and compliance, they do not significantly drive short-term profitability.

Key words: Audit, Financial Disclosure, Financial Performance, DT Saccos, Kenya

1. Introduction

Savings and Credit Cooperative Organizations (SACCOs) operate under stringent regulatory frameworks designed to ensure transparency, accountability, and the protection of members' interests. Regulatory bodies, such as the cooperative regulatory authority or central bank in various countries, mandate a set of disclosures that SACCOs must adhere to firms. Regulation disclosures among financial statements refer to the mandatory information that organizations, including financial institutions like Savings and Credit Cooperative Organizations (SACCOs), are required to disclose as per regulatory requirements. These disclosures are imposed by regulatory bodies to ensure transparency, accountability, and protection of stakeholders' interests. The aspects of regulation-induced disclosures in UK aim to promote financial stability, prevent fraud, and enhance members' confidence in the cooperative movement in Australia (Xiao et al., 2023).

Regulation disclosures are essential for fostering trust and confidence in financial institutions, which in turn supports their long-term sustainability and growth. In United Kingdom, disclosure of audited financial statements including the auditor's opinion on the accuracy and fairness of the financial statements affect performance. Disclosure of transactions with related parties, including directors, shareholders, and affiliated entities are regulated. These disclosures empower members to make informed decisions, build trust in the SACCO, and safeguard their financial interests. SACCOs must disclose their compliance with regulatory requirements, including adherence to prudential standards, reporting obligations, and licensing conditions. Members should have confidence that the SACCO operates in accordance with applicable laws and regulation (Impink et al 2016).

The major aspects of regulation disclosures for SACCOs include requirements that these entities regularly file and disclose their financial performance. In particular, these financial entities are required to make disclosures of total assets, current and non-current assets, liabilities and shareholders' equity in their statement of financial position (Pawlewicz, 2018). Equally, SACCOs are mandated to publish statement of income, which sometimes is referred to as profit and loss statement, with a clear breakdown of total revenues, operating revenues, costs, and net income earned over specified period. Regulatory requirements also mandate financial reporting of SACCOs to detail cash flows from operating, investing and financing activities as well as notes to statements and auditors unqualified opinion (Belay & Jesen, 2020).

Ensuring members have access to relevant information pertaining to their share contributions, loans balances, and interest rates are key to maintenance of transparency and accountability to members. This means, at the request of members, SACCOs should be in a position to furnish them with relevant information pertaining to membership, contribution, loan balance and interest rates. In China, SACCO are mandated by law to ensure members have access to information pertaining to their, savings, dividends, and loan terms. As part of the effort to promote transparency, accountability, and trust between management, board and members, it is imperative that members have access to relevant information as discussed. By providing clear and comprehensive information about members' rights, obligations, and financial transactions, SACCOs empower members to make informed decisions, protect their interests, and participate effectively in the cooperative's governance and activities (Cui et al., 2023).

Under governance and compliance disclosures, SASRA stipulates each SACCO must have a board of directors that oversees its operations in compliance with statutory requirements. The board is responsible for ensuring proper and accurate records are maintained (SASRA, 2022). Each SACCO is also mandated to have Supervisory Committee who oversees board activities on behalf of members such that they file annual reports to members. Governance and compliance requirements mandate that information concerning board members, composition of the board including gender and qualification as well as that of supervisory committee members be in the public domain. This includes details about board meetings, decisions taken, and any conflicts of interest. SACCOs are required to disclose information about their governance structure, including the composition of the board of directors, supervisory committee, and management team. Members should know who is responsible for overseeing the SACCO's operations and ensuring compliance with regulations (Pawlewicz, 2018).

Generally, regulation-induced disclosures in SACCOs play a crucial role in promoting transparency, accountability, and trust between the SACCO and its members. By providing relevant information in a timely and accessible manner, SACCOs can empower their members to make informed financial decisions and contribute to the sustainable growth and development of the cooperative (Malahim 2023).

The core mandate of SASRA ranges from Licensing of deposit-taking SACCOs (DT-SACCOs) and recently to non-deposit-taking SACCOs (NDTS) meeting certain thresholds, supervision of Saccos and regulation as well as enforcement of prudential guidelines. The authority ensures SACCOs operate transparently, especially in dealings with members and promotes fair lending, proper disclosure of terms, and resolution of member complaints. It facilitates adoption of sound financial practices in SACCOs and encourages digital transformation, innovation, and financial inclusion. Recent developments suggest that SASRA now regulates non-deposit taking SACCOs with assets greater than KES 100 million. Equally through digital solutions there is increased scrutiny of mobile lending and Fintech partnerships involving SACCOs and implementation of a more proactive and targeted regulatory approach based on risk assessment. These Saccos operate of their main legal frameworks that is Sacco Societies Act, 2008 – Primary legislation for licensing and regulation, Sacco Societies (Deposit-Taking Sacco Business) Regulations, 2010 and Sacco Societies (Non-Deposit Taking Business) Regulations, 2020.

There are 345 SACCOs are now under SASRA regulation: 178 deposit-taking (DT) and 177 non-deposit-taking (NDTS) SACCOs licensed for January 1 to December 31, 2025. In January 2025, SASRA revoked licenses of two Nairobi-based NDTS SACCOs—B-SMART and MULTIPLE because of non-renewal of authorization and compliance failures. Public notices were issued warning SACCOs against investing members' funds in unregulated entities, mandating the recall of such investments.

According to 2023 Supervision Report Membership rose to 6.84 million (6.57% YoY increase), covering ~30% of Kenya's adult working population while loan portfolio grew 11.5% to KShs. 758 billion, and deposits increased by 9.95%, leading SACCOs to rely more on share capital and retained earnings. The report highlights ongoing issues with governance and remittance non-compliance, prompting SASRA to explore policy reforms including tribunal expansion.

1.1 Global Perspective of Performance of SACCOs

SACCOs play critical role in the expansion financial services especially among the world's underserved population as such financial health of these institutions is of great relevance. (Pasara, Makochehanwa & Dunga, 2021). According to Otieno et al., (2013) the link between regulatory environment and financial performance among SACCOs is of critical importance as these institutions play an outsized role enhancing financial inclusion. Criticality of the sector explains why regulatory frameworks often pay attention to profitability, liquidity, efficiency, and credit quality and strength of financial performance. According to Hertog (2007), vitality of regulation environment in the performance of financial institutions, more deposit taking institutions has been key to development of several theories including public interest theory which is of the view government regulation of financial

institutions is key to safeguarding the public interest. For this reason, it is important to understand how presence of various regulations including disclosures on financial metrics actually affects the performance of SACCOs.

From a global perspective, regulatory disclosure can be construed to mean mandatory reporting and transparency requirements imposed on organizations by regulatory bodies. These disclosures are intended to enhance accountability, protect stakeholders' interests, and improve the overall transparency of financial operations (Menezes 2023). In the context of Savings and Credit Cooperative Organizations (SACCOs), such regulations can have significant implications for their financial performance. In the United States, SACCOs are often referred to as credit unions. The regulatory framework governing credit unions is stringent, with the National Credit Union Administration (NCUA) playing a key role. Key regulation-induced disclosures include the reporting of financial statements, lending practices, and risk management strategies. The impact on financial performance is generally positive as these disclosures foster trust and confidence among members and investors, which can lead to increased deposits and membership growth. However, compliance costs can be high, potentially impacting smaller credit unions.

Regulatory disclosures are meant to protect the health and soundness of financial performance of industries that are considered strategic to economic growth and development. The financial industry being one of the key pillars of the Kenyan economy has been subject to numerous regulatory requirements aimed at guaranteeing the performance of the industry. To this end, SACCOs in Kenya have been subject to increased level of regulation, more so from the Sacco Societies Regulatory Authority (SASRA), a regulatory body overseeing some 359 SACCOs a total asset base 890.31 billion in 2022, 620.45 billion in mobilized deposits, and a loan portfolio amounting to 680.35 billion. With a membership base of 6.42 million, it is clear that the financial performance of SACCOs in the country is of great importance not only to SASRA but also to the government of Kenya.

1.2 Regional Perspective of Performance of SACCOs

In Africa, more so in Sub-Saharan Africa, SACCOs play a critical role in enhancing financing inclusion more in rural farming communities who have limited access to commercial banking services, which for a long time have been based mainly in leading commercial centers across the region. The critical role that SACCOs in enhancing financial inclusion and serving underserved communities has seen various government across the region enact laws aimed at safeguarding the performance of these institutions as well as that of the public, more so of its members (Ndegwa & Koori, 2019).

In Ghana, the regulatory body for SACCOs, often called credit unions, is the Bank of Ghana. Regulation disclosures that have a direct influence on the operations of SACCOs in Ghana include the requirement to submit audited financial statements, disclose loan portfolios, and report on liquidity and capital adequacy (Essandoh, 2018). These regulations aim to ensure the soundness and stability of SACCOs. The impact on financial performance is mixed. While increased transparency can enhance member trust and attract more deposits, the cost of compliance can be burdensome for smaller SACCOs, potentially affecting their profitability (Erin and Okika 2023).

Ethiopian SACCOs are regulated by the National Bank of Ethiopia. Disclosures required by regulation include financial reporting, audits, and details on loan performance. These measures are intended to safeguard the financial health of SACCOs and protect members' savings. The impact on financial performance can be significant, with transparency potentially leading to greater member confidence and increased financial stability. However, the regulatory burden may pose challenges, particularly for smaller SACCOs with limited resources (Vikiru and Moronge 2023).

Across these regions, the impact of regulation-induced disclosures on the financial performance of SACCOs shows both commonalities and differences. In more developed regulatory environments like the United States, the benefits of enhanced transparency and member trust generally outweigh the compliance costs, leading to positive financial outcomes. In developing countries such as Ghana, Ethiopia, Uganda and Kenya, while the transparency brought about by these disclosures is crucial for building trust and stability, the costs of compliance can be disproportionately high for smaller SACCOs, potentially affecting their profitability and sustainability (Kyabarongo et al 2024)

1.3 Kenyan Perspective of Performance of SACCOs

In Kenya, SACCOs are regulated by the Sacco Societies Regulatory Authority (SASRA). Regulation disclosures that directly influence the performance of SACCOs in the country include regular financial reporting, risk management disclosures, and compliance with capital adequacy requirements. These disclosures have generally had a positive impact on the financial performance of SACCOs by improving transparency and member confidence, leading to growth in membership and deposits. However, the cost of compliance can be a significant factor, particularly for smaller SACCOs (Nthiwa 2021).

In Kisii County, Kenya, the local impact reflects the broader national trends but is particularly significant due to the essential role of SACCOs in the local economy. Effective regulation and transparency can lead to improved financial health and growth for SACCOs, but balancing these benefits with the costs of compliance remains a critical challenge (Oino 2018).

Focusing specifically on Nairobi County, Kenya, SACCOs are a crucial part of the local financial ecosystem, providing essential financial services to the community. The regulatory disclosures mandated by SASRA are crucial for maintaining the trust and confidence of members. In Nairobi County, these regulations have had a notable impact on the financial performance of SACCOs. Enhanced transparency and accountability have led to increased member trust and deposit mobilization. However, as in other regions, the cost of compliance remains a challenge, particularly for smaller SACCOs that may struggle with the administrative burden and financial costs associated with meeting regulatory requirements.

1.4 Regulation of Deposit Taking SACCOs (DTs)

Savings and credit co-operatives (SACCOs) in Kenya are organized into two key categories; deposit taking SACCOs and Non-Withdrawable Deposit Taking SACCOs. Licensing and regulation of these financial entities is overseen by the SASRA. The law stipulates all DT-Saccos must be licensed and abide by requisite regulatory framework to operate. Essentially, all DT SACCOs in the Country, which total 357 are licensed and regulated by SASRA. As part of its mandate, SASRA has adopted risk-based framework for regulating the operations and financial performance of DT-SACCOs operating in the country. The regulatory framework that govern operations of DT-SACCOs is designed to enhance the financial health of these entities by ensuring they comply with routine requirements such as filing of financial statements such as balance sheet statement, profit and loss statement, cash flows statement. These entities are also required to meet capital adequacy and liquidity requirement, which is critical to continued performance of these institutions.

Deposit-taking SACCOs in Kenya can be categorized into three categories; large, medium and small sized SACCOs. SASRA uses a standard template in determining the size of Saccos, which essentially specifies the regulatory framework they have to meet. SASRA focuses on the loans, deposits and asset base Njuguna (2012). Small Saccos are considered those with asset base of below 1 Billion while Saccos with savings between one and three billion are considered medium while Saccos with over four billion are large Saccos. While the total number of DT-SACCOs in the country is 357 as of 2022, the number of cooperatives in the country is quite totaling to 10,800 registered co-operative societies with a six million strong membership. The sector is quite critical to economic growth and development in country, accounting for as high as 31% of the country's savings and as high as 6.8% of Kenya's gross domestic product (GDP).

2. Statement of the Problem

The financial sector in Kenya, particularly the Savings and Credit Cooperative Organizations (SACCOs), plays a crucial role in providing financial services to a significant portion of the population. SACCOs are vital for promoting financial inclusion, economic development, and social welfare. The sector has been recognized across the globe, more so among developing countries for its contribution to economic growth and development. According to SASRA, (2022), DT-Sacco's account for as high as 31 percent of Kenya's savings and are responsible for 6.8% of Kenya's GDP. The sector's contribution to economic growth also extends to the thousands of jobs it contributes directly and indirectly. DT-Sacco's have also proved integral to growth of business investment, where the level of lending has been growing for years. Despite this positive view, the sector the sector has faced challenges related to transparency, accountability, and financial stability, which have led to concerns about the adequacy of financial performance reporting and overall governance (Kyabarongo et al, 2024). Strict compliance to the disclosure requirements improves transparency, ensures accountability, safeguarding of the limited resources at the disposal of Saccos and in effect this translates to improved financial performance.

Despite existence of a regulatory framework aimed at shielding Sacco's from various challenges that directly, affect financial performance of these entities; existing statistics on performance shows return on asset ratio (ROA) for DT-Sacco's declined from 2.65% in 2020 to 1.59% in 2021, which signifies a significant drop in profitability. Similarly, capital adequacy, which assesses the extent an institution, can cover its obligations solely from capital declined from 11.3% in 2020 to 9.15% (SASRA, 2022). To this end, several studies have studied the potential effect of regulatory disclosure requirements on financial performance of SACCOs.

Despite enhanced regulatory efforts by SASRA that places more attention on financial reporting, transparency and accountability through mandatory disclosures, there is limited empirical evidence on the impact of these regulation-induced disclosures on the financial performance of SACCOs in Nairobi County. While Gatu, Njehia and Kimutai, (2023) examined the relationship between SASRA's prudential regulations and financial performance of DT Sacco's, the study was limited to capital adequacy and liquidity requirements hence the need for this study which includes audit quality and governance and compliance disclosures as part of the independent variables. As such, this study fills the gap in literature by providing insights into the effectiveness of regulation-induced disclosures in achieving their intended outcomes, thereby contributing to better regulatory practices and improved financial performance in the SACCO sector.

3. Study Objective

The main objective of the study was to determine the effects of audit quality report disclosure on the financial performance of Deposit- taking SACCO's in Nairobi County.

4. Literature Review

4.1 Theoretical Review

4.1.1 Agency Theory

Agency theory was developed by economists Michael Jensen and William Meckling in 1976. Agency theory explores the relationship between principals (e.g., SACCO members) and agents (e.g., SACCO management). This theory addresses issues of trust and conflicts of interest between the agent and the principal, suggesting that regulatory disclosures can help mitigate agency problems by aligning the interests of management with those of the members (Lundberg 2022). Agency theory underscores the importance of regulation disclosures in mitigating agency problems by enhancing transparency, accountability, and trust between principals and agents.

Several assumptions underscore the relevance of the principal-agent relationship including the view agents and principals have different goals that if left unregulated leads to conflict of interest. The theory is also assumes the agent-principal relationship is characterized by existence of information asymmetry, necessitating the need for mandatory regulatory disclosure on firm performance (de Camargo et al., 2018). The theory is also of the position voluntary disclosure by agents is motivated by the desire to influence perception concerning firm activities hence the need to regulate the manner in which such information can be released.

Despite being highly relevant in shaping relationship between shareholders of a company and management, agent theory has been criticized for being simplistic. Critics argue the theory is overly simplistic by assuming that shareholders are rational actors with well-defined objectives, which is always not the case (de Camargo, 2018). Failure by the theory to take into account of other stakeholders such as employees, customers and the government who affect whose behaviour might have detriment impact on firm performance.

Based on the assumptions that underpin the agency theory including the view agents and principals have different goals, mandatory regulatory disclosures help to align the interests of managers and shareholders, in the process reducing information asymmetry, and ensuring adequate monitoring mechanisms are in place (Mwita, 2022). As a result, they play a crucial role in promoting good corporate governance and improving the overall financial performance of organizations (Khandelwal et al 2023). Regulation disclosures enhance transparency and accountability, reducing information asymmetry between management and members. This can lead to improved trust and better financial performance reporting as management is held accountable for their actions. To this end, the agency theory is relevant to this study as it explains the necessity of regulation disclosures for SACCOs.

4.1.2 Signaling Theory

Signaling theory, initially developed by Michael Spence in 1973 to address knowledge gaps between firms and potential workforces, has found applicability in various domains beyond accounting. It has been adapted to fields like Human Resource Management, business, and financial markets due to its intuitive nature and wide-ranging implications. However, in accounting, the idea was initially proposed by Amotz Zahavi in 1975. Its importance in accounting significantly increased after Alan Grafen formally demonstrated in 1990 that 'honest' signals can be an evolutionarily fixed approach. Signaling theory suggests that organizations use disclosures as a signal to convey their quality and reliability to the market. High-quality disclosures signal strong governance, financial health, and operational integrity (Zhong 2022).

Regulation-induced disclosures act as a signal to members and potential investors about the SACCO's financial health and management's commitment to transparency, which can enhance the SACCO's reputation and attract more investment.

Signaling theory highlights the strategic importance of risk disclosures for SACCOs. By providing clear, comprehensive, and credible risk disclosures, SACCOs can effectively reduce information asymmetry, build trust and confidence among stakeholders, demonstrate their competence and stability differentiate themselves from competitors, ensure regulatory compliance, and strengthen member loyalty.

4.2 Empirical Review

Carcello, Hermanson and Ye, (2011) examined audit quality report disclosure, corporate governance research in accounting and auditing: Insights, practice implications, and future research directions. The impact of audit quality disclosures on financial performance has been a significant area of research within accounting and finance. This review synthesizes empirical studies that explore how audit quality affects financial performance. The study used corporate governance and audit quality (independent variable), and financial performance (dependent variable). Agency Theory was used. Archival research using corporate governance data and financial performance metrics from publicly traded companies were adopted. Regression analysis to assess the relationship between audit quality indicators (such as auditor reputation and audit fees) and financial performance measures (e.g., return on assets, return on equity). High-quality audits, characterized by reputable auditors and higher audit fees, are

associated with better financial performance. The study suggests that improved transparency and reduced information asymmetry enhance investor confidence, leading to improved financial outcomes.

Defond and Zhang, (2014) reviewed on Audit Quality and Financial Reporting Integrity. The study used variables included on Audit quality (independent variable), financial misstatements, and financial performance (dependent variables) was used. Signaling Theory and Agency Theory were used. The methodology and literature review of archival auditing research, focusing on studies examining audit quality and its effects on financial reporting and performance. Qualitative syntheses of empirical findings from various studies were used. High-quality audits reduce the likelihood of financial misstatements and fraud. Companies with higher audit quality show fewer restatements and improved financial performance. The signaling effect of audit quality reassures investors about the accuracy and reliability of financial statements.

Verbruggen, Christian and Millis (2015) evaluated audit quality and Nonprofit Organizations' Compliance with Reporting Standards on performance. The study used variables with Audit quality (independent variable), compliance with reporting standards, financial performance (dependent variable). Resource Dependency Theory, Institutional Theory were used. Survey and archival research of nonprofit organizations in Belgium were used. Multivariate regression analysis was used to examine the relationship between audit quality and compliance with reporting standards, and its subsequent impact on financial performance. Nonprofits with higher audit quality demonstrate better compliance with reporting standards, which is positively associated with financial performance. Enhanced compliance driven by quality audits improves stakeholder trust and funding opportunities.

Cohen, Krishnamoorthy and Wright (2017) studied the effect of audit quality in Enterprise Risk Management and Financial Reporting. Audit quality (independent variable), risk management effectiveness, financial performance (dependent variable) was used. Agency Theory, Risk and Management Theory were used. The study used Interviews and surveys of audit committee members, CFOs, and external auditors in large corporations. The study used thematic analysis of qualitative data, supplemented by regression analysis of survey data. High-quality audit reports enhance the effectiveness of enterprise risk management (ERM) practices, leading to better financial performance. Effective ERM, supported by robust audit processes, helps in identifying and mitigating financial risks, thus contributing to financial stability and performance.

Cohen (2017) investigated the effect of audit quality disclosures on financial performance of enterprises. Empirical studies consistently show that high-quality audit report disclosures positively affect financial performance through enhanced transparency, reduced information asymmetry, improved compliance, and better risk management. The synthesis of these studies, grounded in theories such as agency theory, signaling theory, and resource dependency theory, provides a robust framework for understanding the critical role of audit quality in financial performance reporting.

5. Research Design

A research design is essentially a blueprint of conducting a research study (Kothari, 2004) which essentially implies that it provides the framework of carrying out the study. Descriptive research design is adopted in this study. Descriptive studies are said to describe the phenomenon as it is without alteration. The design was used successfully by Mwita, (2022) and Omimo, (2014) to study the how compliance to SASRA regulations on liquidity and capital adequacy affected the performance of SACCOs in Nairobi County and Kisumu County respectively.

The study focused on SACCOs with operations in Nairobi County. As the leading commercial and financial center in Kenya and the entire East-African region, Nairobi was deemed viable for examination of how mandatory regulation affects the performance of DT-SACCOs in the City. Specifically, the study targeted SACCOs regulated by SASRA with operations within the Nairobi's CBD.

The target population is an aggregate of individuals who share common characteristics or character traits. In the context of the present study, all the finance/accounts staff working with the Saccos to constitute the target population. The foregoing employees were chosen due the reasoning that they will be the most conversant individuals relative to issues touching on regulation-induced disclosures on financial performance. The target population of 601 respondents comprised of 49 SACCOs employees. These Saccos are regulated by the Sacco Societies Regulatory Authority (SASRA), ensuring they meet certain standards and provide safe and reliable services to their members.

A common confidence level of 95%, which corresponds to a Z-score of 1.96 and a typical margin of error is 5% (0.05) was applied is sample derivation. The study utilized the Yemane 1967 sampling formula to determine the sample size as formulated;

$$n = N / (1 + N (r^2))$$

To cater for non-response the sample was increased by 30 percent. Therefore, the required sample size was approximately 377 respondents.

Various methods of collecting primary data were adopted in the inquiry such as questionnaires and interviews. The questionnaire was adopted as the principal data collection instrument because it is to be administered across the board. This instrument was principally structured and designed carefully to ensure that it carries questions capable of providing answers to all the research questions. As an instrument design strategy, complete structuring of the questionnaire was relevant for analysis purposes when coding and tabulating information. Structured questions were essential in ensuring that the respondents do not divert from the required response required by the researcher.

The relevant permits were obtained prior to data collection. A formal letter was obtained from the University to be allowed to move on with data collection. This was followed by obtaining the consent of administration of the management. The questionnaires were issued to the sampled respondents through their respective sectional heads and supervisors. The respondents were allowed approximately 5 working days to fill them. The filled questionnaires were collected from the respondents through sectional heads.

After cleaning, editing and coding, all the collected data were analyzed using quantitative approaches. The study used descriptive statistics such as frequency distribution and percentages to facilitate the change of raw data into a form that was easy to understand and interpret in relation to the study variables. Pearson correlation coefficient was used to determine the degree of association between dependent variable (financial performance) and independent variables (Audit quality disclosures, Capital adequacy and liquidity disclosures, Risk management disclosures and Governance disclosures). Multiple regression was used to establish the effect if independent variables on the dependent variable.

6. Research Analysis and Findings

6.1 Descriptive Statistics

The researcher sought to understand the characteristics of the audit quality disclosure constructs and the results are as presented in table 1.

Table 1: Audit Quality Disclosure

	Mean	S. D.
A1: Sacco accounts are prepared in accordance with international financial reporting standards	4.11	.815
A2: All the Sacco returns are signed by at least two authorized signatories before submission to the Authority	3.99	.974
A3 Sacco provides all the required reports on net value of earnings on net value of earnings arising from financial services	4.02	.908
A4: There is a full disclosure of the liabilities of our Sacco	4.10	.761
A5: Sacco does financial position reporting on a full disclosure basis	4.13	.718
A6: Auditing and reporting on a monthly, quarterly and annually as per the regulations	4.10	.778
A7: The Sacco provides voluntary disclosure on all financial reports	4.10	.794
A8: Board members have autonomy and freedom in decision making	4.08	.789
Audit Quality Disclosure	4.080	.3581

The results show that respondents generally agreed that their SACCOs adhere to strong audit and reporting standards. The mean scores of the individual items ranged between 3.99 and 4.13 on a 5-point scale, with an overall composite mean of 4.08 (SD = 0.36), indicating a high level of compliance and transparency in audit quality practices. The relatively low standard deviations across items (ranging from 0.71 to 0.97) suggest consistency in responses and shared perceptions among participants.

Specifically, the highest-rated item was financial position reporting on a full disclosure basis (M = 4.13, SD = 0.718), demonstrating strong commitment to transparency in financial position reporting. Close behind were adherence to international financial reporting standards (M = 4.11, SD = 0.815) and regular auditing as per regulations (M = 4.10, SD = 0.778). The lowest, though still positive, was the requirement for all SACCO returns to be signed by two authorized signatories (M = 3.99, SD = 0.974), suggesting slightly less consensus on this practice.

The overall implication is that SACCOs in the study maintain robust audit quality disclosure mechanisms, which enhance accountability, build member trust, and improve financial transparency. Strong audit and disclosure practices are critical for SACCOs' financial performance and sustainability, as they minimize risks of mismanagement; ensure regulatory compliance, and foster confidence among stakeholders.

6.2 Inferential Statistics

To determine the nature and strength of the relationship between the independent variables and financial performance of Saccos Karl Pearson Coefficient of correlation was used.

ROE shows negative but statistically insignificant correlations with AQD ($r = -.272$). This suggests that although the financial and governance dimensions are important for stability and risk management, they do not directly translate into short-term profitability. It may also imply that profitability depends more on other factors such as operational efficiency, diversification of income streams, or external market conditions. The correlation results provide valuable insights into the factors influencing the financial performance of Saccos in Kenya.

Simple regression model was tested to examine the effect of the Asset Quality Dimension (AQD) on Financial Performance

Table 2: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.272 ^a	.074	.038	.7727467

Source: Field Data 2025

Correlation ($R = .272$), the model shows a weak positive correlation between AQD and ROE. This indicates that while there is a relationship, it is not particularly strong. Coefficient of determination (R Square = .074) in the model means that it explains 7.4% of the variance in ROE. This means that AQD accounts for a small portion of the changes in financial performance (ROE), while the remaining 92.6% is explained by other factors not included in the model. After adjusting for sample size and predictors, the explanatory power slightly reduces to 3.8%, reinforcing the conclusion that AQD alone has a limited effect on Sacco profitability. The relatively large standard error indicates that actual ROE values vary considerably from those predicted by the model, again suggesting low predictive accuracy.

The findings suggest that while asset quality is important for the stability and risk management of Saccos, its direct impact on profitability, as measured by ROE, is limited. This reinforces the earlier correlation analysis, which showed a negative and insignificant relationship between AQD and ROE. Therefore, the financial performance of Saccos appears to be influenced more strongly by other factors such as capital adequacy, governance, loan portfolio diversification, and external market conditions.

While maintaining strong asset quality ensures that Saccos remain solvent and avoid non-performing loans, profitability is more likely to be driven by efficient intermediation, cost control, governance effectiveness, and diversification of income sources. From a strategic perspective, this finding suggests that Sacco managers cannot rely solely on asset quality improvements to drive profitability. Instead, they need a holistic approach that integrates robust capital adequacy, governance practices, innovative lending strategies, and digital financial services to achieve sustainable financial performance.

To determine the goodness of fit of the regression model F and p-values from table 3 were used.

Table 3: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.242	1	1.242	2.079	.161 ^b
	Residual	211.935	355	.597		
	Total	213.177	356			

Source: Field Data 2025

The ANOVA results indicate that the regression model is not statistically significant ($F(1, 355) = 2.079, p = .161$). This implies that the model does not significantly improve the prediction of the dependent variable over the mean-only model. In other words, the independent variable does not explain a statistically significant portion of the variance in the dependent variable at the 5% level of significance.

The regression model explained only a small proportion of the variance in the dependent variable, as evidenced by the low F-statistic and non-significant p-value. The lack of statistical significance suggests that there is insufficient evidence to support a meaningful linear relationship between the predictor and the outcome variable in this case.

Table 4: Regression Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	Constant	3.101	1.910		1.624	.116
	AQD	-.833	.578	-.272	-1.442	.161

The regression results reveal that the unstandardized coefficient (B) for AQD is -0.833, which implies that for every one-unit increase in AQD, the dependent variable (e.g., Return on Equity - ROE) is expected to decrease by 0.833 units, assuming all other factors are held constant. However, the p-value associated with AQD is 0.161, which is greater than the conventional threshold of 0.05. This indicates that the relationship between AQD and the dependent variable is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no linear relationship between AQD and the outcome variable cannot be rejected.

The standardized coefficient (Beta) of -0.272 indicates a weak negative relationship between AQD and the dependent variable in standardized terms, meaning that a one standard deviation increase in AQD results in a 0.272 standard deviation decrease in the outcome variable. Despite this negative association, the relationship is not statistically significant.

The constant (intercept) value of 3.101 represents the expected value of the dependent variable when AQD is zero. However, the p-value for the constant is also not significant ($p = 0.116$), suggesting that it is not statistically different from zero at the 5% level. The regression analysis indicates that AQD does not have a statistically significant effect on the dependent variable. While the direction of the relationship is negative, the lack of significance suggests that AQD is not a strong predictor in this model. These findings are consistent with the earlier ANOVA results, which also indicated the model was not statistically significant overall.

7. Conclusions and Recommendations

The study concludes that SACCOs in Nairobi exhibit strong adherence to audit quality disclosure standards, as demonstrated by a high composite mean score of 4.08 and low standard deviation ($SD = 0.36$). This suggests consistent audit practices across institutions, particularly in areas such as full disclosure and compliance with international financial reporting standards. Although the correlation between Audit Quality Disclosure (AQD) and Return on Equity (ROE) was negative and statistically insignificant, the presence of robust audit mechanisms enhances transparency and accountability. AQD was found to explain 7.4% of the variation in financial performance, indicating a moderate influence. Therefore, while audit quality may not directly boost profitability, it plays a pivotal role in reinforcing financial sustainability and institutional trustworthiness.

Although SACCOs demonstrated strong adherence to audit quality standards, the relationship with financial performance (ROE) was weak and statistically insignificant. To strengthen the impact of audit quality on performance, it is recommended that SACCOs adopt beyond compliance, using them as tools for strategic financial planning leverage audit outcomes and operational improvement. Further, internal audit functions should be strengthened through capacity building, automation, and integration into strategic decision-making. Also, regulatory bodies like SASRA should encourage SACCOs to adopt data-driven audit systems that enhance transparency while providing actionable insights for performance improvement.

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